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**ANALYSIS OF THE CONDITION OF TEETH AND THE INFLUENCE OF
EXTERNAL FACTORS ON THE OCCURRENCE OF TUMORS IN THE
ORAL CAVITY**

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ANNOTATION

Late diagnosis of head and neck tumors is associated with insufficient oncological awareness among patients, inadequate knowledge regarding precancerous conditions, and infrequent dental visits, which is reflected by the unsatisfactory condition of oral organs and tissues. In addition, exogenous factors such as residence in large industrial cities, smoking, and employment in hazardous industries negatively influence the initial dental status of patients in this category.

Keywords: head and neck tumors, oral sanitation, smoking, precancerous conditions.

Introduction. Tumors of the head and neck region include neoplasms affecting the oral cavity, and timely diagnosis of these lesions remains possible only through early clinical recognition. Despite advances in modern medicine, management of patients with oral cancer continues to represent a major clinical challenge.

The five-year survival rate of affected patients remains unsatisfactory. This is primarily associated with the fact that approximately 70–80% of patients are diagnosed at stages III–IV, when malignant tumors have already developed locally advanced forms, substantially complicating treatment.

According to statistical data, the cure rate for stage III oral cancer is approximately 35–52%, while in stage IV it decreases to 5–10% [1,4].

Modern classification of oral cavity malignancies includes the following anatomical localizations (TNM classification, 2002):

1. Oropharyngeal tumors:

- tumors of the anterior wall of the oropharynx (base of the tongue and vallecular region);
- valleculae;
- tumors of the lateral wall of the oropharynx;
- palatine tonsils;
- tonsillar pillars;
- glossotonsillar sulcus;
- tumors of the posterior wall of the oropharynx;
- tumors of the superior wall of the oropharynx:
 - inferior surface of the soft palate;
 - uvula.

2. Oral cavity tumors:

- tumors of the oral mucosa:
 - mucosa of upper and lower lips;
 - buccal mucosa;
 - retromolar region;
 - oral vestibule (upper and lower);
- upper alveolar process and gingiva;
- lower alveolar process and gingiva;
- hard palate;
- tongue tumors:
 - anterior two-thirds of the tongue including lateral borders;
 - inferior surface of the tongue;
 - floor of the oral cavity.

Malignant neoplasms of the oropharyngeal region continue to demonstrate increasing prevalence worldwide. According to statistical reports [4], between 1995 and 2005 the average annual growth rate of malignant tumors localized in this region reached approximately 0.54% among both sexes (55.5% in men). In addition, the incidence among women has increased significantly during the last decade. Growth rates reached 21.52% and were especially pronounced among individuals aged 31–97 years. During the same period, approximately 340,000 new cases of oropharyngeal cancer were registered globally [1].

In Uzbekistan, 15,031 new cancer cases were identified in 2020. According to both national and international statistical data, the frequency of these neoplasms varies considerably, accounting for up to 30% of all malignant tumors [1].

Analysis of oral cavity tumors demonstrates that this pathology is considerably more common among men (ratio 2–3:1). Patient age ranges from 20 to 80 years; however, the majority are physically active individuals between 40 and 60 years of age, with an average age of approximately 55 years.

Incidence of oral cancer is strongly associated with social and environmental factors, including climatic conditions, nutrition, and lifestyle. In certain countries, prevalence demonstrates marked geographical variation. These indicators are particularly high in India and comparatively lower in Sweden. In Uzbekistan, incidence of oropharyngeal cancer reached 5.05 per 100,000 population in 2020, while mortality from malignant neoplasms of the oropharyngeal region accounted for 5.85 cases per 100,000 population in 2005. Although recent years have shown stabilization of head and neck oncology indicators (2010 – 5.63; 2020 – 6.19), annual growth rates continue to increase by approximately 6.9%.

Consequently, oral and oropharyngeal cancers represent an important medical and social problem in Uzbekistan. Analysis of patients treated in the Samarkand Regional Oncology Center demonstrated pronounced deterioration of dental status among these individuals.

Purpose of the study. To investigate the influence of dental condition and exogenous factors on development of malignant tumors of the oral cavity.

Materials and methods. The study included analysis of dental status in 586 patients diagnosed with malignant neoplasms of the oral cavity. Distribution of tumor localization was as follows:

- oral cavity — 147 patients (25%);
- tongue — 195 patients (33%);
- oropharynx — 139 patients (24%);
- upper jaw — 36 patients (6%);
- lower jaw — 12 patients (2%);
- oral mucosa — 21 patients (4%);
- nose — 4 patients (1%);
- soft palate — 18 patients (3%);
- retromolar area — 14 patients (2%).

The obtained results correspond with previously published epidemiological data presented by A.G. Prikhodko (2008). Among men, tumors of the oral cavity and oropharynx were most frequently observed (up to 59.7% and 49.6%, respectively). Among women, tumors of the nose (25%), retromolar region (21.4%), and upper jaw (19.4%) predominated.

The relatively young age of affected patients confirms the substantial social significance of malignant oral diseases because approximately 55.7% of patients belonged to the economically active population. These findings correspond to previously reported observations [4].

Development and progression of oral malignancies are associated with local traumatic factors and harmful habits such as smoking, considered one of the major carcinogenic influences. Strong alcoholic beverages, trauma caused by damaged teeth or orthopedic structures, poorly manufactured prostheses, and occupational exposure to chemical compounds and high temperatures also contribute to carcinogenesis.

Among the examined patients, 350 individuals (60%) were smokers, while 44 patients (58.8%) regularly consumed strong alcoholic beverages.

Unfavorable occupational conditions, exposure to wind, temperature fluctuations, and industrial hazards also play an important role in development of head and neck cancers [5]. In our study, the majority of patients (471 individuals, 80.4%) were residents of large industrial cities. Among them, 171 patients (29.3%) had worked for prolonged periods in major industrial enterprises under conditions involving elevated temperatures, increased dust exposure, and contact with volatile chemical compounds.

Even patients diagnosed with breast cancer require regular dental and dispensary examinations. However, our study demonstrated that only 6.2% of patients had received information regarding precancerous conditions before disease onset, and only 24.8% underwent regular oral examinations annually.

Information regarding diagnosis of oropharyngeal cancer and preventive dental consultations was also assessed. Many patients reported prolonged use of removable prosthetic appliances and chronic trauma of the oral mucosa caused by defective teeth and residual roots. Evaluation of the initial dental status was important not only for assessment of severity of oral complications but also for determining the scope and timing of planned treatment and rehabilitation.

Despite differences in social status and lifestyle, patients demonstrated similar baseline dental conditions. Comparative analysis between study groups was performed using conventional dental examination methods, including assessment of oral hygiene and the DMFT index (Decayed, Missing, and Filled Teeth).

Clinical dental examination included objective assessment of the teeth and oral cavity. Oral tumors were classified according to the TNM system recommended by the World Health Organization (Geneva, 1997). In addition, patients' ability to maintain oral hygiene procedures during hospitalization was evaluated. The simplified oral hygiene index (OHI) according to Podshadley and Haley (1968) was used. Salivary secretion was also investigated in all patients.

Table 1. Assessment of Oral Hygiene Status in the Main and Comparison Groups

Group	Good (0.1–0.6)	Satisfactory (0.7–1.6)	Poor (≥1.7)	Mean index (M±m)
Main group (n=195)	78 (39.8%)	109 (56%)	8 (4.2%)	1.3±0.1
Comparison group (n=391)	140 (36%)	228 (54.8%)	23 (5.6%)	1.5±0.2
Total (n=586)	218 (37.2%)	337 (57.5%)	31 (5.6%)	1.4±0.1

Analysis of the obtained results demonstrated that the average oral hygiene index among examined patients was 1.4±0.1, corresponding to a “satisfactory” hygiene level (Table 1). Among 586 patients with malignant tumors of the oral cavity, oral hygiene practices generally corresponded to standard normative values.

Survey data showed that 83.6% of patients brushed their teeth twice daily, 10.2% brushed once daily, and 6.2% did not brush regularly. The DMFT index (Decayed–Missing–Filled Teeth) was used to evaluate prevalence and intensity of dental caries.

Table 2. Assessment of Dental Caries Intensity (DMFT Index)

Group	Decayed teeth	Filled teeth	Missing teeth	Mean index
Main group (n=195)	23±0.3	10±0.3	18±0.2	17±0.3
Comparison group (n=391)	19±0.2	6±0.4	14±0.3	13±0.4
Total (n=586)	21±0.3	8±0.4	16±0.3	15±0.4

The obtained findings demonstrated that patients with malignant tumors of the oral cavity had a mean DMFT index of 15±0.4, including a significant number of missing teeth. These indicators emphasize the necessity for regular preventive dental care.

For salivary analysis, unstimulated mixed saliva was collected. After rinsing the mouth, saliva was collected into a graduated tube over 1.5–2 hours. Patients were instructed to remain calm, maintain a lowered head position, avoid swallowing or moving the lips, and allow saliva to accumulate naturally throughout the collection period. Saliva accumulated over 2 minutes was transferred into a test tube, and the procedure was repeated twice more. Total collection time was 6 minutes. Salivary flow rate was calculated in ml/min based on total saliva volume collected.

Table 3. Assessment of Sialometric Indices in the Main Group During Hospitalization

Group	Salivary flow rate (ml/min) (M±m)
Main group (n=195)	4.0±0.04
Comparison group (n=391)	3.96±0.03
Total (n=586)	3.98±0.04
Statistical significance	$p \leq 0.05$

At the time of hospitalization, all patients demonstrated signs of non-inflammatory xerostomia, while salivary gland function remained generally preserved. The mean unstimulated salivary flow rate at admission was 3.98 ± 0.04 ml/min, slightly lower than standard physiological values in individuals without this pathology.

Data obtained during the study were recorded in the medical history and outpatient dental records of patients. Initial dental examinations revealed unsatisfactory oral conditions. Only 4.8% of patients examined at the Samarkand Regional Oncology Dispensary, Head and Neck Department, and oral sanitation unit complied with satisfactory oral hygiene standards. Furthermore, 95.2% of patients required specialized dental treatment, which also indicated inadequate oral hygiene status.

Among all patients, 176 individuals (30%) consulted a dentist because of complaints, 155 patients (26.5%) were referred by oncologists, 107 patients (18.3%) by otorhinolaryngologists, and 103 patients (17.7%) presented independently with

complaints. Analysis of collected anamnesis demonstrated that 59.2% of patients had attempted self-treatment before seeking specialized care. However, by the time they consulted healthcare professionals, both oncological and non-oncological conditions had often already progressed beyond stages amenable to conservative therapy.

Management of oral mucosal diseases was performed according to standard clinical protocols. According to established recommendations, treatment of mucosal lesions should initially be conducted by dental specialists. If pathological changes persist for more than two weeks despite conservative therapy, patients should be referred for oncological examination (Filyurin M.D., 1997).

The study demonstrated that patients who did not consult a dentist or oncologist regularly for 1–3 months accounted for 52.4% of cases; 28.6% delayed consultation for 4–6 months; and 19% sought medical attention only after more than one year. In many cases, these delays were associated with diagnosis of tumors at advanced stages III–IV.

Conclusion. The obtained findings indicate that patients with oral malignancies frequently present with unsatisfactory conditions of oral organs and tissues. Most patients demonstrated insufficient oncological awareness and did not undergo regular dental examinations. Late diagnosis of malignant disease and delayed referral to specialists resulted in hospitalization of many patients at stages III–IV of tumor progression, which subsequently complicated treatment outcomes.

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